

ALTRUITIC BEHAVIOR AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF THE PRE-ADOLESCENTS

Kishor Roy¹, Dr. Asoke Kumar Saha² and Sanjida Shahid Juthi³

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Jagannath University,
Dhaka, Bangladesh. E-mail: kishorkumar433@yahoo.com

² Professor & Chairman, Department of Psychology, Jagannath University,
Dhaka, Bangladesh. E-mail: asoke_saha@yahoo.com

³ MS Student, Department of Psychology, Jagannath University, Dhaka.
E-mail: sanjidajuthi1991@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study attempted to explore differences between altruistic behavior and social responsibility of the pre-adolescents. A total of 200 respondents participated in this study as sample. Participants were divided into two groups according to place of residence (rural and urban). Each group was again equally subdivided into boys and girls. A Measure of Helping Behavior (MHB) developed by Enam (1992) and Bengali version of Social Responsibility scale (Haq et al., 1984) were used for data collection. The results of the study were analyzed by using *t*-test. Results of the present study indicated that there was a significant difference between the urban and rural participants on altruistic behavior and no significant differences on social responsibility. It was also found that there were no significant differences between male and female participants on altruistic behavior and social responsibility.

Keywords: *Altruistic behavior, social responsibility*

Introduction

Society as an organization involves helping behavior. Ordinarily each member of societal organization is dependent on other members in everyday activities. This dependency of an individual to another individual moves from interpersonal to inter-group relationship. If we can't interact and socialize with those around our life will be extremely difficult. If we want to lead a social life we should help with one another. In any social situation, we continuously get involved with pro-social behavior that is also known as altruistic behavior or helping behavior. The word altruism, which comes from the Italian Altruism, was coined in 1851 by August Comte to refer to benevolence. Although everyone are not agree today on what precisely altruism entails, the most basic definition is seeking the welfare of others. Altruism refers to an act performed voluntarily to help someone else when there is no expectation of receiving a reward in many form, except perhaps a feeling of having done a good deed (Schroeder, Dovidio, and Piliavin, 1995). Thus the act of benefiting others is inherently determined in children through the process of socialization. According to Kohlberg (1963) "altruistic behavior is based on certain social norms such as reciprocity, morality, social responsibility and individual ability to apprehend the need of the situation. Thus the act of doing well to others in inherently determined in children through the process of socialization". Ugurel-Semin (1952) was found that the children between 4-6 years age group 69%, 7-8 age group 84%, 8-9 age group 77%, 9-10 age group 100%, 10-11 age group 93%, and 11-12 age group expressed 97% helping behavior. Mannarion (1973) conducted experiment on altruistic behavior and he found that adolescent boys were involved in a chum relationship exhibited in significant greater levels of altruistic behavior than those without a chum. Eagly and Crowley (1986) found that men are indeed more likely to help in chivalrous, heroic ways, and women are more likely to be helpful in long term relationships that value greater commitment. A large number of participants have been conducted to find out gender differences in helping behavior of children as well as adults. However, results reported in the studies on gender differences are not consistent. For example, no gender differences were documented in helping behavior for nursery school children (Fischer, 1963; Hartup and Keller, 1960). In western societies, gender has been shown an important factor in helping behavior,

although results have been contradictory. Rural pre-adolescents have been found to be more likely to help than urban pre-adolescents (Feinman, 1978). Korte, Ypma, & Toppen (1975) found that busy or noise surroundings reduce the likelihood of people noticing that someone needs help. No doubt this is one reason that people are more likely to help in quiet, rural areas than in crowded cities (Esenberg & Fabes, 1998).

The other variable social responsibility can be defined as a tendency to help others without expecting any immediate personal reward (Berkowitz & Daniel, 1964). According to Dovidio (1991) “Social responsibility is associated with individual character as well as many situational variables”. Social responsibility is an ethical theory that an entity, be it an organization or individual, has an obligation to act to benefit society at large. Social responsibility is a duty every individual or organization has to perform so as to maintain a balance between the economic development, in the material sense, and the welfare of the society and environment.

Campbell (1975) suggested that genetic evolution may help explain a few basis pro socially behavior such as parent’s caring for their young, but that it does not apply to more extreme instances of helping a strangers in distress. Human societies have gradually and selectively evolved skills and beliefs that promote the welfare of the group. Because pro socially behavior generally benefits society, it has become part of the social rules or norms. A norm of social responsibility prescribes that one should help other who depend on him. Every person should have the responsibility to his society although social norms have determined the pattern of responsibility. Social responsibility provides a cultural basis for pro social behavior. Through the process of socialization, individuals learn these rules and come to behave in accord with this guideline for pro socially behavior. Researcher showing that people are more likely to help relatives and friends than strangers can be explained in terms of social norms, people feels greater responsibility for those who are close to them and assume that they will help them if a need arises (Dovidio, 1991). Schwartz (1986) in his analysis of situations, in which moral choices arise, suggests two conditions that must be satisfied before an individual will feel compelled behave in accordance with a moral norm. First, the person must define the situation as one in which his act have consequences for the welfare of others, and second, the situation must be defined as one in which he ascribes to himself responsibility for those acts and their consequences. He found that participants who generally saw themselves as willing to assume responsibility and who were sensitive to the consequences of their behavior did tend to conform to altruistic norms. Intuitively it appears that the degree of social involvement and social responsibility are closely related phenomena.

Rationale of the study

From the above literature it is evident that social responsibility is one of the major determinants of Pro-social behavior. In Bangladesh, people from urban and rural area varied in their behavior in the context of environment setting. Urban life is becoming over crowded, socially insecure and relation with others is very much superficial. Urban people are less interacting with their neighbors compare to rural people. It is revealed that social responsibility plays crucial role on altruistic behavior from the literature review. Thus measure of altruistic behavior and social

responsibility of urban and rural pre-adolescents can be important in the context of personality development of Bangladesh. Pro social behavior is facilitated by the presence of relevant dispositional variables. There is no such study on dispositional factors of personality in Bangladesh context. It is worthwhile to explore the differences between urban and rural pre adolescent's altruistic behavior and social responsibility. The study of altruistic would help us to understand an act of virtue and its role in the social system. However, the study would have some applied values and give new knowledge about helping behavior in the context of Bangladesh. The findings of the study can be helpful to those social organizations who are working on preadolescents groups.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were-

1. To examine the gender difference in altruistic behavior of the pre adolescents.
2. To investigate the difference in altruistic behavior of the pre adolescents according to place of residence.
3. To examine the gender difference in social responsibility of the pre adolescents.
4. To investigate the difference in social responsibility of the pre adolescents according to place of residence.

Methods

Sample

The number of participants of the study consist 200 children. They were selected from four schools of Dhaka city and four schools of rural area. The respondents were categorized equally into groups on the basis of their place of residence, (rural = 100 and urban= 100). Each group was again equally subdivided into boys (N= 100) and girls (N= 100) according to their gender difference. Each cell included 50 subjects and total number of subject was $(50 \times 4) = 200$. They were selected by the purposive sampling method.

Measuring Instruments

Following instruments were used to measure altruistic behavior and social responsibility.

Measure of Helping Behavior (MHB)

The scale called "Measure of Helping Behavior" (MHB) developed by Shahuria Enam (1992). There were 12 items in MHB. Each item of the list was a 5 point Scale with the response categories "I do it always", "I do it sometimes", "I do not know", "I do not do it", "I never do it",. Individuals respond to MHB items on five point Scale rating from "I do it always" (5) and "I never do it" (1).

To determine the reliability of the Measure of Helping Behavior (MHB), the criterion of split-half was obtained with odd and even numbers of the 16 items (N=40) as used in the pilot study and the correlation was found to be .48. Split-half reliability was again computed from the

scores in final study (N=240) with odd even number of 12 items and the correlation was found .67. After applying Spearman Brown Prophecy formula, the co-efficient was found to rise from .67 to .80 which was very high. Thus it can be said that the reliability of the Measure of Helping Behavior (MHB) is statistically sound and it is highly reliable. The co-efficient of correlation between two equivalent forms of the test in the pilot study (N=40) was .48 and that of final study in comparison to pilot study is an indication of the predictive validity of the Measure of Helping Behavior (MHB). Besides the face validity was measured of the MHB scale.

Social Responsibility Scale

An adapted Bengali version of social responsibility scale (Haq,et. al., 1984), originally developed by Berkowitz and Lutterman (1968) was use for measuring social responsibility. The scale contained eight items, for each of the eight items the respondent was to give one of the five answers ranking from ‘strongly agree’ to ‘strongly disagree’. The statements were so constructed that for some. Responsibility was indicated by agreement and for others it was indicated by disagreement. For those items where agreement was the index of responsibility scale value increased in the direction of agreement while for the items where disagreement was the indicator of responsibility the scale value increased in the reverse direction. The sum of the value of all the scale point marked by a respondent constituted the social responsibility score. The highest score was 40 and the lowest was 8. Highest score indicated greater social responsibility. The reliability of Bengali version of the scale was tested by administering both English and Bengali versions of the scale on a group of Dhaka University students (N=50) with an interval three weeks. Product moment correlation co-efficient between the two scale was .54.

Procedure

To collect the data from the schools, permission was sought from the concerned authorizes. Data were collected individually from the respondents. Along with the written instruction within the questionnaires, the participants were also given verbal instruction to ensure that they had understood the task. The respondents were told that the information given by on the completion of the task, each participant was thanked for their cooperation.

Results

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the altruistic behavior and social responsibility of urban and rural pre-adolescents. *t*-test was applied to see whether altruistic behavior differed according to place of residence. The results are presented in following table.

Table 1

The difference of altruistic behavior between male and female.

Gender	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>
Male	100	51.51	4.97	198	.36
Female	100	51.26	4.84		

p < .05

Table 1 shows that there are no significant difference of altruistic behavior between male and female pre-adolescents ($t = .36$) at .05 level. It also shows that the mean score obtained by the male pre-adolescents ($M = 51.51$) is higher than the female pre-adolescents ($M = 51.26$).

Table 2

The difference of altruistic behavior between rural and urban pre-adolescents.

Residence	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>
Rural	100	52.45	3.53	198	3.14*
Urban	100	50.32	5.79		

* $p < .05$

Table 2 shows that the mean scores obtained by the rural pre-adolescents ($M = 52.45$) is higher than the mean score obtained by the urban pre-adolescents ($M = 50.32$). It also shows that mean difference in altruistic behavior of urban and rural respondents is significant ($t = 3.14$) at .05 level.

Table 3

The difference of social responsibility between male and female pre-adolescents.

Gender	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>
Male	100	29.32	3.34	198	.753
Female	100	29.68	3.41		

$p < .05$

Table 3 shows that the mean score obtained by the male pre-adolescents ($M = 29.32$) is lower than the female pre-adolescents ($M = 29.68$). It also shows that mean difference in social responsibility between male and female pre-adolescents is not significant ($t = .753$) at .05 level.

Table 4

The difference of social responsibility between rural and urban pre-adolescents.

Residence	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>
Rural	100	29.84	3.24	198	1.42
Urban	100	29.16	3.48		

$p < .05$

Table 4 shows that there are no significant difference of social responsibility between rural pre-adolescents ($t = 1.42$) at .05 level. It also shows that the mean score obtained by the rural pre-adolescents ($M = 29.84$) is higher than the urban pre-adolescents ($M = 29.16$).

Discussion

The findings of the present study (table 1) indicate that gender has no significant difference in altruistic behavior of the pre-adolescents. The finding is consistent with the findings of earlier researches (Staub, 1968). Despite the stereotype that girls share, help, and conform other people more than boys do, most studies of gender differences in children's prosocial behaviors have found no difference between boys and girls. However, when differences have been found, they appear to be slightly more likely to favor females. Even when differences favoring girls have been found, they may not reflect true differences in prosocial responding. Girls tend to be viewed as more prosocial by others, and therefore may be rated as more helpful by teachers and peers even if they really are not. Indeed, males may be more helpful than females when helping involves instrumental rescuing or helping behaviors (for example, helping to change a flat tire) or potential danger (for example, picking up a hitchhiker). In contrast, girls and women may be more likely to help when psychological assistance (for example, comforting) is needed, and when the recipient of help is an acquaintance, friend, or child.

In summary, although boys may perform some types of altruistic behaviors more than girls do, there are no clear sex differences in altruistic behavior. In previous time altruistic behavior of boys was higher than girls probably because boys tend to overestimate themselves while girls tend to be underestimated in our society. Parents, teachers and peers give less importance to the girl's achievements. Besides this, boys were more adventurous. Now a day's parents, teachers and peers give more importance to the girl's achievements. It may be assumed that decreasing gender discrimination; change in child rearing practice, increasing social support of female children there was no gender difference in altruistic behavior.

Another important finding presented in table 2 showed that rural children are more altruistic than their urban counterparts. This result also supports the findings of some previous researches (Hedge and Yousif, (1992). Steblay (1987) found that the people of rural areas are more altruistic than urban or city areas. Urban social environment is quite different from rural social context in many ways. Parental control is more in every sequence of the urban children compared to rural children. Urban children are learned not to interact with neighbors and unknown persons due to social insecurity. Urban neighborhoods have little impact on once life sharing, cooperation. Urban life continues with constant strains and constant noise.

In Dhaka city parents do not feel secure to leave alone their children to go to school, or any other places to play or make contact with relatives. Busy cities always make noise that cannot help children to develop good mood in helping behavior or other good intentions to help others. These may cause the difference in altruistic behavior of urban and rural pre-adolescents. Traditional cultures in which people live in extended family groups and share work seem to foster pro-social values. In our culture people are generally helpful and encourage the act of altruistic behavior. If people get the opportunity to interact with different levels of people, it may help them to learn about the altruistic nature of human based on the social norms. The rural children get better opportunity than the urban children may be due to this opportunity rural children are more altruistic than urban children. Table 3 showed that gender has no significant difference in social responsibility of the pre-adolescents. This finding is consistent with the

findings of other researchers (Mamlin et,al, 2001). Now a day's girls are more serious about their right and their position. They are more aware about all social responsibility and overcome all social restriction. They achieve higher position in the society. Beside this it may be assumed that decreasing gender discrimination, increasing social support of female children there was no gender difference in social responsibility.

Another important findings presented in table 4 showed that there are no significant difference of social responsibility between rural and urban pre-adolescents. It may be explained that due to daily life behavior practice of children are freer to take decision in their life. Their parents do not control their each and every behavior of the children. It may be because of personality pattern develop in children. That is why children can take the responsibility of their own.

Conclusion

The present study attempted to explore differences between altruistic behavior and social responsibility of urban and rural male and female pre-adolescents. Results of the present study indicated that there was a significant difference between the urban and rural participants on altruistic behavior and no significant differences on social responsibility. It was also found that there were no significant differences between male and female participants on altruistic behavior and social responsibility. However, the study has its limitations too because of some practical reasons like time and financial constraint. The researcher had to select the sample only from four schools of Dhaka city and four schools of rural area. Lastly, there are other variables which influence altruistic behavior and social responsibility of pre adolescents which are not investigated in the present research. However, further studies are suggested by including other variables which may affect altruistic behavior and social responsibility of pre adolescents like age, mood, socio-economic status, personality pattern, family structure, genetic influences etc. In conclusion, it may say that this study has its own merits in throwing lights into an area which needs attention and further research.

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